

Pathogen Associated Molecular Patterns in *Candida albicans*: Insights into cell wall structure and immune interactions

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Cell Wall of *C. albicans* - Pathogen Associated Molecular Patterns (PAMPs)

The molecular organization of the cell wall of *S. cerevisiae* has been studied extensively, providing a substantial amount of generic information that can be used as a model for understanding and comparing the cell wall properties with other known species (Lipke and Ovalle, 1998; Cabib et al., 2001; Klis et al., 2002; Klis et al., 2006). However, it is also clear that different species of fungi differ markedly in their cell wall structure, and *S. cerevisiae* diverged from *C. albicans* about 200 million years ago. The cell wall is important because it maintains the architecture of the cell, protecting the cell from osmotic changes within the environment and maintaining the overall cell shape. The outer cell wall layer of heavily glycosylated and convoluted mannoproteins confers protection to the underlying essential skeletal network of polysaccharides against hydrolytic enzymes, as well as phages and toxins (De Groot et al., 2005; Klis et al., 2001; Klis et al., 2006; Klis et al., 2009) (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3 *C. albicans* cell wall structure and PAMPs.

The *C. albicans* outer cell wall consists mainly of mannoproteins (35-40%). These are attached via GPI-anchored linkages to β -1,6 glucans (20%), to the inner layer of β -1,3 glucans (40%), and chitin (2%) (Netea et al., 2008; Klis et al., 2009). This composition changes according to different niche environments—for example, exposure to caspofungin and other β -1,3 glucan-damaging agents leads to an increase in chitin content (Walker et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2012). In budding yeast cells, a scar is left on the mother cell, and the inner chitin and glucan of this scar remain exposed at the surface (Gantner et al., 2005). The architecture of the outer cell mannoproteins is stabilized by O-linked and N-linked glycosylation. These glycoproteins have many important virulence functions, serving as adhesins, invasins, and carbohydrate-degrading enzymes. They also represent dominant antigens of the cell surface. O-linked mannans are characterized by modification by an ether-linked linear oligosaccharide of up to five α -1,2 mannose sugars. N-linked mannan consists of a conserved core that is highly conserved among eukaryotes and a highly elaborated, branched outer chain formed on an α -1,6 backbone, which is fungal-specific (Munro et al., 2005; Munro et al., 2007; Hall and Gow, 2013). These cell wall components are important as Pathogen Associated Molecular

Patterns (PAMPs) and interact with the Pathogen Recognition Receptors (PRRs) present on immune cells (Netea et al., 2008) (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1. 3 *C. albicans* cell wall structure and PAMPs.

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